

ECONOMY

THE GREAT SILK ROAD: EMPOWERING AZERBAIJAN-GEORGIA ECONOMIC COOPERATION

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Abstract

The Great Silk Road is a historical trade route that connected the East and the West, facilitating the exchange of goods, ideas, and culture between different civilizations. This ancient network of trade routes played a significant role in shaping the economic landscape of many countries, including Azerbaijan and Georgia. This article explores the influence of the Great Silk Road on the economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and Georgia, highlighting the shared heritage, revival of trade routes, and the mutual benefits and growth resulting from this historical connection.

Keywords: Silk road, economic cooperation, trade, bilateral relations.

Azerbaijan and Georgia have been working towards strengthening their economic cooperation in recent years. The objective is to enhance trade relations, promote investment opportunities, and foster collaboration in various sectors. Both countries recognize the potential benefits of closer economic ties, including increased job opportunities, technological exchange, and regional stability. Efforts have been made to improve transportation infrastructure, streamline customs procedures, and facilitate cross-border trade. Additionally, initiatives are being undertaken to promote tourism, cultural exchanges, and people-to-people contacts between Azerbaijan and Georgia. The aim is to create a conducive environment for economic growth and mutual prosperity in the region [3].

The One Belt One Road initiative, also known as the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), has significant implications for Azerbaijan and Georgia. Both countries view the BRI as an opportunity to enhance their economic cooperation and strengthen their positions as regional transit hubs. Azerbaijan, with its strategic location and key transportation routes, such as the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway and the Baku International Sea Trade Port, plays a crucial role in the Middle Corridor of the BRI. This corridor offers a shorter and more cost-effective route, benefiting both countries and providing political advantages for China. The BRI also helps diversify the national economy, strengthens the Azerbaijan-Georgia-Turkey strategic triangle, and increases Azerbaijan's political maneuverability by balancing Russia's influence in the region [2].

A Shared Legacy The city of Sheki, nestled in the picturesque landscapes of Azerbaijan, proudly carries the legacy of the Silk Road. Known for its silk industry, Sheki's silk factory has become a significant economic contributor to the region. By utilizing traditional techniques, silk cloth is produced from cocoons, showcasing the rich heritage of craftsmanship. The popularity of *kelaghayi* (hand-stamped silk scarfs) has surged, attracting both domestic and international markets [5].

The recent geopolitical challenges in neighboring countries, such as Iran and Russia, have led to a resurgence of trade routes through the Caspian Sea, Azerbaijan, and Georgia. These strategic routes have gained

significance in facilitating the flow of goods, fostering economic growth, and deepening bilateral ties. The historical importance of the Silk Road has played a pivotal role in reestablishing Azerbaijan-Georgia economic cooperation [5].

In recent years, Azerbaijan and Georgia have made significant efforts to revive the trade routes that once thrived along the Great Silk Road. These initiatives aim to strengthen economic cooperation and foster regional integration. The restoration of transportation infrastructure, such as railways, highways, and ports, has facilitated the movement of goods and people between the two countries. Additionally, the development of special economic zones and free trade agreements has further encouraged trade and investment in the region.

China's ambitious Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) aims to revitalize ancient trade routes, including the Silk Road. Azerbaijan has actively participated in this initiative, recognizing the potential for enhanced economic cooperation. Through infrastructure projects like the Baku-Tbilisi-Kars railway and the Baku International Sea Trade Port, Azerbaijan has deepened its ties with China, facilitating trade and opening new avenues for investment [4].

The Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), launched by China in 2013, has also played a crucial role in enhancing economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and Georgia. As part of this ambitious project, both countries have actively participated in the development of infrastructure, energy, and trade networks. The BRI aims to create a modern-day version of the Great Silk Road, connecting Asia with Europe through a network of land and maritime routes. Azerbaijan and Georgia, being strategically located at the crossroads of these routes, have become important participants in this initiative, opening up new avenues for economic growth and cooperation.

The Great Silk Road has an influence on the development of trade relations between Azerbaijan and Georgia, and as a result, the trade turnover between the two countries has increased over the years. The table below shows the trade turnover between the two countries in different years.

Trade turnover between Azerbaijan and Georgia

	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Trade turnover	468108,3	561905,5	592324,2	659027	536202,9	761236,9	771781,5
Import	51464,3	74148,3	94073,6	72122,9	74293,5	100194,2	136117,2
Export	416644	487757,2	498250,6	586904,1	461909,4	661042,7	635664,3

Source: "<https://www.stat.gov.az/>" [1]

The influence of the Great Silk Road on Azerbaijan-Georgia economic cooperation is mutually beneficial. Both nations have embraced the opportunity to strengthen their trade relations, fostering economic growth and regional stability. Bilateral trade between Azerbaijan and Georgia has witnessed a significant increase, reflecting the success of collaborative efforts. Moreover, the Silk Road heritage has attracted tourists, providing an additional boost to the local economies [4].

The influence of the Great Silk Road on Azerbaijan-Georgia economic cooperation has led to mutual benefits and growth for both countries. Trade between Azerbaijan and Georgia has flourished, with the exchange of goods ranging from agricultural products and energy resources to manufactured goods and textiles. The improved connectivity and trade facilitation measures have boosted bilateral trade and investment, leading to increased economic opportunities for businesses and individuals in both countries.

Furthermore, the cultural exchange resulting from the historical ties between Azerbaijan and Georgia has enriched the tourism industry in both countries. Travelers from around the world are drawn to the region's rich heritage and diverse landscapes, contributing to the growth of the hospitality sector and creating employment opportunities for the local population.

The Great Silk Road has left a lasting impact on the economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and Georgia. The shared heritage, revival of trade routes, and participation in initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative have strengthened the bilateral relations and created a solid foundation for future growth and prosperity.

As both countries continue to invest in infrastructure development, trade facilitation, and cultural exchange, the economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and Georgia is poised to reach new heights. The historical connection provided by the Great Silk Road serves as a reminder of the potential for mutually beneficial partnerships and paves the way for a prosperous future for both nations.

In conclusion, the Great Silk Road has played a crucial role in empowering the economic cooperation between Azerbaijan and Georgia. From the shared heritage of the silk industry in Sheki to the revival of trade routes and participation in initiatives like the Belt and Road Initiative, the influence of the Great Silk Road has fostered mutual benefits and growth. As both countries continue to build on this historical connection, the potential for a prosperous future is immense, solidifying the importance of the Great Silk Road in Azerbaijan-Georgia economic cooperation.

Conclusion:

The Great Silk Road continues to leave an indelible mark on Azerbaijan-Georgia economic cooperation. From the vibrant silk industry in Sheki to the revival of trade routes, this historical network has facilitated trade, cultural exchange, and regional stability. The Belt and Road Initiative further strengthens the partnership, opening new horizons for economic growth. As Azerbaijan and Georgia embrace their shared heritage, the Great Silk Road paves the way for a prosperous and interconnected future.

References

1. Azerbaijan State Statistics Committee - <https://www.stat.gov.az/>;
2. B.Babayev, F.İsmailzade – Azerbaijan`s contribution to the Chinese Belt&Road Initiative (BRI);
3. CENTER FOR INTERNATIONAL PRIVATE ENTERPRISE ;
4. China Daily global edition - <https://global.china-daily.com.cn/a/201810/20/WS5bca82bca310eff30328380c.html>;
5. CNN travel - <https://edition.cnn.com/travel/>;
6. M.Tsereteli - Azerbaijan and Georgia: Azerbaijan and Georgia: Strategic Partnership for Stability in a Volatile Region, Silk road paper https://www.silkroadstudies.org/resources/pdf/SilkRoadPapers/2013_09_SRP_Tsereteli_Azerbaijan-Georgia.pdf;
7. The Politicon online platform <https://politicon.co/az/analytics/33/azerbaijan-and-belt-and-road-initiative-on-the-way-of-becoming-a-regional-transport-center>.